

A commoner query on missing intermediates for four variants, the appearance of intermediate for omicron, the delay in declaring SARS-COV-2 as airborne with a revisit to Schrodinger's "What is life?"

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Abstract

This article raises questions on the absence of intermediates or conduits for the first four variants, alpha, beta, gamma, and delta of SARS –COV -2. Was the lack of intermediaries or conduits due to a breach in the lower limit 30 for physical factor W/KT ? A range of 30 to 60 for W/KT is mentioned in "What if life" by Schrodinger to estimate the time of expectation of mutation $t = \tau e^{(W/KT)}$ ($\tau = 10^{-14}$ sec, a constant, W lift, K , Boltzmann constant, T , Absolute temperature). Did W/KT go to a low value for the ultrafast production of SARS-COV-2, to bypass an intermediate or conduit resulting in not declaring the airborne nature of SARS-COV-2? Did the appearance of a host (mice) for omicron provide the methodology of SARS-COV-2 to be declared airborne? The popular narrative for the origin of SARS-COV-2 is either from animal wet markets or lab leaks. If the origin of SARS-COV2 is due to quantum stress in animals from ultra-stress conditions in a wet market, then a global shake-up for organizing wet markets is required. If it is due to a quantum leak from a lab due to Gain of Function Research (GOFR), then the ethics of performing GOFR has to be seriously considered.

Keywords: SARS-COV-2 , missing intermediate, mice intermediate. wet markets .
Gain of function, ethics.

1.0 Introduction

The debate over the origin of SARS-COV-2 is not only being discussed in scientific circles but also by common folks since SARS-COV-2 gave an **invisible egalitarian shock and awe** resulting in millions of deaths and serious health issues. This article raises some queries with respect to the origin of SARS-COV-2. (wet markets or lab leak) and puts forward the possibility of ultrafast production of SARS-COV-2 with reference to the limit of 30 being breached to very low value for the physical factor W/KT (Schrodinger, 1992) Either it should be setting the wet markets in order or have a serious look at the ethics of Gain of Function Research (GOFR).

2.0 The missing intermediate in SARS-COV 2

References from the article "Why an Intermediate Host May Not Be Essential for the Evolution of SARS-COV-2 (<https://medium.com/microbial-instincts/why-an-intermediate-host-may-not-be-essential-for-the-evolution-of-sars-cov-2-aa66e0264b57>) are re-referenced and presented in the following lines "Specifically, scientists identified the SARS-CoV-1 and MERS-CoV progenitors sharing 9% genomic identity in palm civets and dromedary camels respectively, confirming their participation as intermediate hosts (Guan et al., 2003; Raj et al., 2014). For Covid-19, the closest hint we have is the pangolin coronavirus, which is about 90 % genetically identical to SARS-CoV-2 (Banerjee et al., 2021). Interestingly, the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the pangolin coronavirus and SARS-CoV-2 is 97.4 % identical at the genetic level suggesting that SARS-CoV-2 might have gotten its RBD from the pangolin coronavirus. (Banerjee et al. 2021), But the 3% genomic difference is still big, especially regarding the crucial RBD that binds to the ACE2 receptor on the cell surface to initiate infection.

Moreover, the pangolins had severe respiratory diseases at sampling (Liu et al. 2020: Xiao et al. 2020), which disfavors its involvement as an intermediate host. "An ideal intermediate reservoir host does not develop severe disease on infection with a virus, a key feature that allows a virus to multiply and seek alternative hosts without killing its evolutionary host," is the premise of a 2020 research review (Banerjee, 2021) Professor David L Robertson's inputs to this medium article are as follows "One of the points the professor clarified is that an intermediate host could mean an active reservoir or simply a conduit for viral transmission.

"With SARS, the civet cats were only a conduit for the transmission of the virus from bats to humans," Prof. Robertson continues, so "bats are the true reservoir species and the civets not necessary for transmission to humans." Conversely, the camels serve as reservoir species for MERS, where camel-to-human spillover can occur repeatedly (WHO report, 2019). This is unlike SARS-CoV-1, where civets are not reservoirs, so they only carry the coronavirus briefly to humans (Wang & Eaton, 2007). With SARS-CoV-2, given that the virus that has emerged is a generalist (able to infect pangolins, minks, cats, and other animals), it is probably not necessary that there is an intermediate species. However, we cannot discount this was the route to humans," Prof. Robertson adds further. "Our study cannot really address this, but what I think we can be confident about is the virus that emerged in humans probably didn't require much adaptation, if any, to be so successful (Maclean, 2021) "In a word, to repeat a point, an intermediate host is not compulsory for SARS-CoV-2 evolution. But whether there is an intermediate host conduit bringing the SARS-CoV-2 progenitor from **bats to humans is unknown**" ([Why an Intermediate Host May Not Be Essential for the Evolution of SARS-CoV-2 | by Shin Jie Yong | Microbial Instincts | Medium](#))

3.0 Omicron variant with intermediate host and beginning the quantum analogy of Schrodinger

Earlier in this article, it was referenced that civet cats were intermediate conduits for SARS, whereas, for MERS, dromedary camels were intermediate hosts. **The famous Rumsfieldian "known unknown "for an intermediate host or conduit for SARS-COV 2 is the important message of the medium article. The first four variants, alpha, beta, gamma, and delta, reported no intermediate hosts (Table 1).** However, evidence that mice were intermediate hosts for the omicron variant from South Africa / Botswana was published in November 2021 (Wei 2021 {a}, Wei 2021 {b}). **Now, this article brings in the quantum analogy of Schrodinger.**

Schrodinger compares quantum physics with no intermediate energies to De Virus's "jump-like" mutations without any intermediate steps. This nonexistence of intermediate steps in De Varies mutations he terms as '**significant discontinuity**' and terms this a "quantum theory of biology." The missing intermediate host resulting in four first variants (Table 1) is analogous to **the 'significant discontinuity' of Schrodinger.** There are two schools of science on the origins of SARS-COV-2. One reported that the virus came from animal wet markets in Wuhan (Andersen et al., 2020). The other school claims it could be a lab leak (Schmidt, 2021). Now

the question is, "Is there anything like "**quantum stress**" when animals are huddled in wet markets for mutations to occur without intermediate hosts or conduits? The other question is, was it a lab leak to bypass the intermediate hosts resulting in something like a "**quantum leak.**" **In the next section, the delay in declaring the airborne nature of SARS COV-2 is discussed with a possible explanation of the science behind the delay.**

4.0 The delay in declaring the "airborne nature "of SARS –COV – 2

The title of a science journalist's article is "Why the WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (WHO) Took Two Years to Say that COVID is Airborne" (Lewis, 2022). Another detailed article, referenced by the science journalist, attributes historical reasons for the resistance to recognizing airborne transmission of SARS-COV-2 (Jimenez et al., 2022). The virus's origin is taken as December 2019 with $t = 0.10$ secs for a physical factor (Delbruck ratio) of 30 (Table 1 & 2). It took two years to declare the virus as airborne (December 2021) after the appearance of the omicron variant in November 2021 (Tables 1& 2). However, there must be **science** for the origins of SARSCOV–2, which bypassed experts employed by WHO. For this, a re-visit to Schrodinger's book "What is Life"? could probably have some insights (Schrodinger, 1992). In an earlier preprint (<https://zenodo.org/record/5939861>), the Polyani-Wigner equation, used by Schrodinger, was invoked to track the journey of SARS-COV-2 and its variants up to omicron. Table 1 from the earlier preprint is recast (<https://zenodo.org/record/5939861>) to indicate the two-year declaration of the airborne nature of the virus. (Physical factor {Delbruck ratio} = 50.2), corresponding to 2.03 years, a little over two years. See the last row in red color in Table 2).

Was the delay in declaring the airborne nature of SARS-COV-2 due to the absence of intermediate hosts or conduits for the first four variants resulting in "significant discontinuity"? Second, did the appearance of the omicron variant on mice as an intermediate host result in SARS-COV-2 to be declared as airborne?

5.0 Gain of Function Research (GOFR)

In this section, the last lines from a reference are quoted verbatim: "With all the challenges inherent in GOFR studies, why do them? Because, some virologists say, the viruses are constantly mutating on their own, effectively doing GOFR experiments at a rate that scientists could never match. "We can either wait for something to arise and then fight it, or we can

anticipate that certain things will arise, and instead, we can pre-emptively build our arsenals," says Morrison. "That's where gain-of-function research can come in handy" (Juliet Morrison, a virologist at the University of California, Riverside, as per the reference) [Dance, 2021]. Now Mother Nature doing GOFR here **is in vivo**, that is, within the system (the vast expanse of planet Earth).

Then in the same article, an **in vitro** (lab-created) experiment is reported performed by Ralph Baric et al. in 2015 as follows "In 2015, virologists led by Ralph Baric at the University of North Carolina in Chapel Hill reported the creation of their own chimera (Menachery, 2015) . They took a version of the coronavirus responsible for the deadly outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in the early 2000s — now known as SARS-COV and adorned it with surface proteins from a different coronavirus taken from Chinese horseshoe bats. In the laboratory, this particular mash-up was able to break into human cells and also make mice ill. This chimera came with a message: Other coronaviruses have the potential to spark a human pandemic. In just a few years' time, that warning would prove prescient, as a distant cousin of SARS-COV has now killed more than 4.9 million people worldwide." The article mentions that some consider this as GOFR, with an adage that the science of introducing new abilities on pathogens needs further study. The meaning of GOFR and how GOFR can help are explained in the Nature article with a discussion on many other issues, including the slugfest between Rand Paul, a Senator with a medical degree (saying it is GOFR), and Anthony Fauci, the then director of National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (saying it is not GOFR) (Dance, 2021). A detailed article on the ethics of GOFR is worth mentioning here (Selegid, 2016).

6.0 Two papers of interest with a revisit to Schrodinger's "What is life"?

The first paper was by Hu B et al., which resulted in the slugfest between Rand Paul and Anthony Fauci (Dance, 2021). The title "**Discovery of a rich gene pool of bat SARS-related coronaviruses provides new insights into the origin of SARS coronavirus**" addresses many issues. (Hu B et al., 2017) . The second paper's title reads, "**The major genetic risk factor for severe COVID-19 is inherited from Neanderthals**". The paper's interesting finding is "Here we show that the risk is conferred by a genomic segment of around 50 kilobases in size that is inherited from Neanderthals and is carried by **around 50% of people in south Asia and around 16% of people in Europe** (Zeeberg & Paabo, 2020). **Earlier, in a**

previous zenodo article, the temperature effect on the time of expected mutation, as mentioned by Schrodinger, was discussed with respect to the delta variant. For emphasis, the temperature effect is reposted here(<https://zenodo.org/record/5939861>)

In Chapter 5, on page 64 Schrodinger writes “ This enables us to test our mutability formula, which as written before was
$$t = \tau e^{W/KT} \quad (1)$$

(It will be remembered that t is the time of expectation for a mutation with threshold energy W.) We ask: How does t change with the temperature? We easily find from the preceding formula in good approximation the ratio of the value at temperature T + 10 to that at temperature T.

$$\frac{t_{T+10}}{t_T} = e^{-10W/KT^2} \quad (2)$$

The exponent being now negative, in equation (2) the ratio is, naturally, smaller than 1. The time of expectation is diminished by raising the temperature, the mutability is increased. Now that can be tested and has been tested with the fly *Drosophila* in the range of temperature which the insects will stand”. The conclusions presented are “temperature influences unstable genes less than stable ones . Is this applicable to SARS-COV-2 ? Inputs on mutations of fly drosophila and SARS-COV-2 if compared could reveal the lowering in time of expected mutations at high temperature.

The origin of delta variant in India was reported as December 2020 (Table 1) during anwinter time in India. The lethal effects of delta variants in India went up from April 2021 , during peak mummer all over India. Increased deaths in summer is presented in earlier preprint [<https://zenodo.org/record/5939861>] (Seetharaman and Kevany, 2021). The question is “ Was there more **stable** genes as mentioned in “What is life”? in the **rich pool of genes** to drastically lower the time of expectation of mutation for SARS-COV-2 (a distant cousin of SARS-COV , Dance 2021) at an increased summer temperature in India? (Hu et al., 2017) . The other paper is related to the serious COVID -19 risk to Neanderthal genes reported to be present in 50% population of South Asia (Zeeberg and Paabo , 2020) . The question is “was the fifty percent population having Neanderthal genes in South Asia an ideal host for mutants (delta variant) from **stable genes in SARS-COV-2 to cause these increased deaths** in the summer of India?

**Table 1 Journey of COVID 2019 and its variants with respect to (W/KT), time of expectation of mutation (t)
Note the declaration of airborne nature of the virus was done after the appearance of Omicron variant
with mice as the intermediate host, whatever be the baseline (start of the pandemic)**

Start of COVID 19 Pandemic declaration Variants	Month/ Year start Pandemic declaration Detection. Of variants	Country of detecting variants./ International health Body in a country declaring the pandemic	t, time of expectation of mutation by equation (1) first row in secs and rest in months.(From Table 1)	Corresponding Delbruck ratio to time 't' as in Table(1) marked in Arial Black
COVID 19 (start)	December 2019	Wuhan China Zhu et al (2020)	0.10 secs	30
Pandemic declared	March 11 th 2020	WHO , Geneva Cucinotta, ,and Vanelli (2020)	3.11	48.14
Variants, (Data from European Centre for Disease Control (ECDC . 2022)				
Alpha	September 2020	United Kingdom	9.07	49.21
Beta VOC	September 2020	South Africa	9.07	49.21
Gamma VOC	December 2020	Brazil	12.17	49.5
Delta VOC	December 2020	India	12,17	49.5
Omicron VOC (<u>mice host , intermediate</u>)	November 2021	South Africa Botswana	23	50.15
Declaration of airborne nature of virus	December 2021 (if December 2019 as baseline) March 11th 2022 (if March 11th 2020 as baseline)	WHO, Geneva declares SARS COV 2 as airborne. Lewis (2022) Jimenez et al (2022)	2.0359 (Table 1) years is taken for both the baselines, with the baseline for March 11th , 2020 declaration of pandemic taken as 3.11 secs.	50.2 50.3if March 11th 2020 declaration taken as baseline.
It has been called COVID 19, December 2019. Omicron in circulation globally, .VOC = Variants of concern; Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta , Omicron				

Table 2: Data on t, time expectation of mutation in secs, minutes, hours,,days , months by , $t = \tau e^{W/KT}$ with respect to W/KT (Delbruck ratio) $\tau=10^{-14}$ sec (note the red colour in the final line , the airborne declaration By WHO).

W/KT	1E-14	t (secs)	t(mins)	t(hrs)	t (days)	t (months)	t (years)
30		0.106865					
31		0.290488					
32		0.78963					
33		2.146436					
34		5.834617					
35		15.86013					
36		43.11232					
37		117.1914	1.95319				
38		318.5593	5.309322				
39		865.934	14.43223				
40		2353.853	39.23088				
41		6398.435	106.6406	1.777343			
42		17392.75	289.8792	4.831319			
43		47278.39	787.9732	13.13289			
44		128516	2141.933	35.69889	1.487454		
45		349342.7	5822.379	97.03964	4.043318		
46		949611.9	15826.87	263.7811	10.99088		
47		2581313	43021.88	717.0314	29.87631		
48		7016736	116945.6	1949.093	81.21222	2.707074	
49		19073466	317891.1	5298.185	220.7577	7.35859	
49.8		42448779	707479.6	11791.33	491.3053	16.37684	
49.9		46913156	781885.9	13031.43	542.9763	18.09921	
50		51847055	864117.6	14401.96	600.0817	20.00272	1.666893
50.1		57299858	954997.6	15916.63	663.1928	22.10643	1.842202
50.2		63326136	1055436	17590.59	732.9414	24.43138	2.035948

7.0 The physical factor (W/KT= 30 to 60) from “What is life?”. Was the lower limit of 30 breached for SARS COV -2 to become globally pervasive without intermediates hosts or conduits.

Schrodinger mentions on Page 52 “that $W = 30KT$ is already rare” at $t = 1/10$ sec. Schrodinger probably is referring to natural mutations of viruses since GOFR is a latter-day curiosity-driven high risk science. The lines from the Nature article are repeated for emphasis “Because, some virologists say, the viruses are constantly mutating on their own, effectively doing GOF experiments at a rate that scientists could never match. “We can either wait for something to arise and then fight it, or we can anticipate that certain things will arise, and instead, we can pre-emptively build our arsenals” (Dance, 2021). So far, so good. Agreed. Two possibilities of the origins of the virus is presented here. First, was there a “**quantum stress**” on animals in an unkept wet market or was it a “quantum leak” from a lab. Was there a violation or breach in the physical factor, say below 30 for both the cases? *The reason for these queries is due to the absence of intermediate hosts or conduits for the first four variants for two years.* The values of 28, 26, 24, 22, and 20 are taken for the physical factor. For this article, we set a limit to 20 and present t, the time of expectation of mutation in secs in Table 3.

Table 3 Physical factor between (W/ KT) 20 and 30 for GOFR using $t = \tau e^{W/KT}$, $\tau =$ small constant, 10^{-14} second. K. is Boltzmann constant. W is the lift. T = absolute temperature.

W/KT	1E-14 t (secs)
30	0.106864746
28	0.014462571
26	0.001957296
24	0.000264891
22	3.58491E-05
20	4.85165E-06

If, W/ KT goes below 20 , the degree of difficulty in declaring virus as airborne would be probably multifold. The physical meaning of the physical factor W/ KT is explained in “What is life ?” is as follows. “it is of the order of the period of the vibrations which takes in the system all the time. You could very broadly describe this factor as meaning that a chance of accumulating the required amount W (lift) though very small, recurs again and again at every vibration, that is, 10^{13} to 10^{14} times every second. **The question is, what would happen to vibrations of 10^{13} to 10^{14} per sec for “quantum stress on wet animals in a wet market or a**

quantum leak with the physical factor 30 going to a low value? **Will it be 10^n with $n \gg \gg \gg$**
14? What will then happen to the accumulation of W ? Will it be more in quantity due to quantum stress or quantum leak compared to Mother Nature's normal mutations or HER GOFR?

The problem of no intermediates or hosts for first four variants, alpha, beta, gamma, and delta probably indicates an ultrafast production of SARS-COV-2. (Table 3) with a possible breach of the physical factor far below 30. Did the omicron variant with the intermediate host (mice) break the **significant discontinuity and** make it possible to declare the airborne nature of SARS-COV-2? In an earlier presentation (<https://zenodo.org/record/5939861>), the origin of SARSCOV -2 was placed at $t = 1/10$ as per "What is life?" or 0.10865 as per Table 1 with t taken as the time of expectation of mutation. This presentation takes a different view from the earlier one, considering the breach of physical factors below 30. Historical reasons are certainly the resistance (Jimenez et al ; 2022). However, with its egalitarian outreach globally, science must be applied rigorously to prevent history from repeating itself so that the global population does not undergo the terrible pain for some unsure gain and scamper from toilet paper to vaccines.

8.0 Summary

The absence of an intermediate host or conduit for the first four variants, alpha, beta, gamma, and delta, raises the possibility of the physical factor (W/ KT) being breached below 30. The limit of 30 being breached to a low 20, as indicated in Table 3, would produce ultrafast SARS-COV-2 or any equivalent virus. The appearance of an intermediate host (mice) for the omicron variant and subsequent declaration of the airborne nature of COVID-19 by WHO raises the possibility of W/ KT being between 30 and 60 and adhere to the Polyani-Wigner expression (post omicron mutations). Did **the stable genes** in the **rich pool of genes** in SARS -COV -2 mutate at a lower time (t) to produce delta variant during summer in India the (high temperature) for it to make a lethal landing on the Neanderthal genes reported to be present in 50 % population in South Asia? **If another pandemic comes , the question is will a host or an intermediate like a mice for omicron slow down the lethal effect of subsequent mutations OR will the virus have nonstop ultrafast ride like the initial four lethal variants of COVID 19 ?**

9.0 Conclusion

Two conjectures on the origin of SARS–COV–2 are in circulation. One is from the wet market animals from Wuhan, and the other is a lab leak. From the start of the 21st century, a new sociology paradigm has come into force. One is the elite, and the other is the non–elite. There has to be a reason for the origin of SARS–COV–2. **If the origin is from wet markets where animals are kept inhumanely, the solution for this non-elitist activity is clean up.** This can be done in coordination with municipalities, PETA, and World Health Organization (WHO). **If, on the other hand, a lab leak is an origin due to GOFR, then it becomes the theatre of elitism.** This theatre should comprise an international elitist star cast for an “International Outlook and Engagement because the risks and benefits of GOFR (can) affect the global community at large; the ethical acceptability of GOFR partly depends on the extent to which it is accepted internationally. Decision and policy-making regarding GOFR should (insofar as possible) involve consultation, negotiation, coordination, and related forms of active engagement with other countries (Selgelid. 2016). In conclusion, suspend or ban GOFR until it is accepted internationally by all countries.

Note:

The uncertainty and pain caused by SARS-COV -2 (Covid 19) on commoners lives including the continuous inconclusive debate on the origin of this virus motivated this presenter to raise questions. Comments, critique on this article welcome.

Dedication:

This article is dedicated to my friend late Vinitbhai Pathak who introduced me to this great book “What is life” (old edition, year of edition not able to recollect)

No potential conflict of interest is reported by the author.

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